

Indonesian Correctional Penitentiary Governance Policy

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Abstract

Frequent riots in prisons between prisoners and officers are a never-ending problem and becoming a problem in Indonesia. Overcapacity and lack of human resources are the trigger factors. As is known, one of the main problems that occur in Indonesian prisons is overcapacity. This is a commitment from the government, in this case the ministry of law and human rights, is needed to find the best solution by providing adequate facilities and infrastructure by increasing human resources, both in quality and quantity. Therefore this research is important to know how the governance of correctional institutions in Indonesia. In this study the authors used qualitative methods through literature study. The result of the study in this research is that the management of correctional institutions in Indonesia is not yet optimal, the problem of law enforcement, lack of facilities and infrastructure and human resources are urgent issues to be resolved immediately.

Keywords: *evaluation, governance, policy, correctional, prison*

INTRODUKTION

In 2017, the number of prisoners and detainees in Indonesia reached 225,025 people. It happened in 2019 when the prisoners burning prison was carried out by inmates in Sorong prison. According to data from kompas.com, there were 258 prisoners escaping on Monday, 19th August 2019, with a total occupancy is 547 people. The next incident in 2019, the prison was again confronted with the burning incident at Sigi prison, the burning of Sigi prison was caused by the inmates' dissatisfaction with the prison. This was followed by riots and arson that took place at the Kabanjahe Detention Center in early 2020, with the provocation of 4 prisoners to oppose the search of rooms in prisons by prisoners. Some of these cases have surfaced in the past year, not to mention several other minor cases that should be of particular concern to the Ministry of Law and Human Rights of the Republic of Indonesia in their handling. With the cases that are always faced by the ranks of the ministry of law and human rights under the Directorate General of Corrections which manages prisons throughout Indonesia, it is a serious problem that must be faced and an evaluation of these various problems needs to be carried out. The basic things faced by the ranks of prisons both from the direction of policy and prison management that must be addressed.

This figure is expected to increase along with the increase in crime in Indonesia. In Indonesia, the prison system uses prisons and detention centers as a means of law enforcement as well as guidance for criminals. However, the number of criminals caught and languishing in iron bars far exceeds the capacity of existing prisons. This situation is referred to as overcapacity or overcapacity which then has an impact on the emergence of various new problems, especially related to the management of detention centers and prisons, where various things occur between prison inmates, riots with officers, escaped detainees and illegal fees and various violations of rules and regulations.

The overcapacity condition is exacerbated by the condition of the number of officers are not balanced with the number of residents. Poor prison governance reached its peak in 2017 with the escape of 200 prisoners from Sialangbuntu, Riau prison. Not to mention other cases related to abuse of facilities and authority of prison officials. Correctional Institutions, hereinafter referred to as prison, have several objectives, one of the objectives is Forming Correctional Assistance to become fully human, aware of their mistakes, improving themselves and not repeating criminal acts so that they can be accepted back by the community and can play an active role in development and can live naturally as good and responsible citizen. This includes the fulfillment of prisoners' rights which are important in a correctional institution. With the system that has been running, the fulfillment of prisoners' rights should be maximally carried out against prisoners.

Improving the health and safety of prisoners in prison means proving that in prison, it is necessary to pay attention to the safety of prisoners as a whole, otherwise it will cause a state of danger to officers and residents in prisons because the violation will have an adverse impact. Overcapacity is also one of the dilemmas that occur in correctional institutions, as a result of the increasing number of residents, the average correctional institution in Indonesia is experiencing overcapacity, the overcapacity that occurs will certainly result in the problem of lack of services for prisoners in prisons.

The rights and obligations of prisoners have been regulated in the Correctional System, which is a new criminal system that replaces the prison system. According to Law Number 12 Year of 1995 concerning Corrections Article 1 number 1, "What is meant by correctional facilities is an activity to carry out the guidance of the prisoners based on the institutional system which is the final part of the criminal system in the criminal justice system. Personal health, both physical and mental, is an important prerequisite for the attainment of welfare and the highest degree of human life". On the basis of these considerations, the right to obtain the highest standard of health is formulated as a human right. Regarding the fulfillment of the right to health, Article 25 paragraph (1) of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) states that everyone has the right to a standard of living adequate for the health and welfare of himself and his family, including the right to food, clothing, housing, and necessary health care and social services, as well as the right to security in times of unemployment, illness, disability, widowhood, old age, or other circumstances resulting in a lack of income, which are beyond his control.

The correctional system is a system of treatment for inmates who adheres to the concept of renewal of imprisonment based on Pancasila and universal humanitarian principles. This system adopts a system of integrating prisoners into society through coaching programs that pay more attention to the rights of prisoners than the old system, namely the prison system. Efforts to achieve the goals of the correctional system include fulfilling the rights of detainees. Recognition of the rights of prisoners can be seen in the contents contained in Law No. 12 Year of 1995 concerning Correctional Article 14 paragraph (1), one of which is the prisoner has the right to receive good health and food services. The recognition of prisoners' rights in this law states that prisoners have the right to get proper health services and food.

Furthermore, Government Regulation Number 32 Year of 1999 about Requirements and Procedures for the Implementation of the Rights of Correctional Assisted Citizens, Article 14 and Article 20 paragraph (1) part four regarding health and food services states that, "Every prisoner and correctional protégé has the right to obtain proper health services". In each correctional facility, a polyclinic and its facilities are provided and at least one doctor and one other health worker are provided. This research becomes interesting to study, how is the governance of correctional institutions in Indonesia. Not only regarding the health problems of the prisoners but also safety and other rights.

RESEARCH METHODS

For this study, the authors use a qualitative descriptive method through literature study. In qualitative descriptive research is carried out systematically, but it is not as rigid as quantitative content analysis. Categorization is only used as a guide, allowing other concepts or categories to emerge during the research process. This research uses literature review related to phenomena that can be studied and observed. The author will first formulate exactly what will be studied in this study. Then, take all actions based on predetermined goals. In this study, the unit of analysis is a reference, a series of words or sentences that indicate something that has meaning in accordance with the correctional institution governance category. Researchers collect news related to prison governance and the rights of prisoners. Content analysis is carried out on electronic, print and online media.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Prison Penitentiary is a place to provide guidance to convicts and correctional students in Indonesia. Before the penitentiary was known in Indonesia, this place was called a prison. Penitentiary is a Technical Implementation Unit under the Directorate General of Corrections, Ministry of Law and Human Rights

(formerly the Ministry of Justice). The occupants of the correctional institutions can be prisoners or prisoners who are still prisoners, meaning that the person is still in the judicial process and has not been determined guilty or not by the judge. Civil servants who handle the development of convicts and prisoners in prisons are called Correctional Officers, or previously known as prison wardens. The concept of correctionalization was first initiated by Justice Minister, Mr. Sahardjo in 1962, that it was stated that the duty of the prison service was not only to carry out sentences, but a much heavier task was to return those convicted to the community. The rise of drug trafficking in Indonesia is also one of the causes of overcapacity at the prison occupancy level. Meanwhile, the State Detention Center is a place where a suspect or defendant is detained during the process of investigation, prosecution and examination in court in Indonesia. The State Detention Center is a technical implementation unit under the Ministry of Law and Human Rights (formerly the Ministry of Justice).

Prisons and detention centers have several similarities. The similarities between both remand centers and prisons are Technical Implementing Units under the Directorate General of Corrections, Ministry of Law and Human Rights. In addition, the placement of residents of remand centers and prisons is equally based on classification of age, sex, and type of crime. Based on Article 18 paragraph (1) Government Regulation Number 27 Year of 1983, in each district or municipality a detention center was formed. However, the condition that occurs in Indonesia is that not all districts and cities in Indonesia have remand centers and prisons, so remand centers are also used to accommodate criminals like prisons. This is also due to the fact that the condition of many prisons in Indonesia, based on information from various sources, has exceeded capacity, therefore the defendants who have served sentences in detention centers, who should have moved from detention centers to serve prison sentences, many remain in detention until their term is over.

Table 3.1.
10 Prisons with the highest overcapacity in Indonesia

No.	Prisons	Capacity	Total of Prisoners	Overcapacity
1.	Bagansiapiapi Prison	98	810	836%
2.	Takengon Prison	65	495	685%
3.	Banjarmasin Prison	366	2.688	664%
4.	Tarakan Prison	155	996	650%
5.	Labuhan Ruku Prison	300	1.770	640%
6.	Tanjung Balai Asahan Prison	198	1.450	632%
7.	Langsa Prison	63	437	594%
8.	Teluk Kuantan Prison	53	363	587%
9.	Bandar Lampung Prison	168	1.055	535%
10.	Lhoksukon Prison	70	433	519%

Source: Data processed from the 2019 Directorate General of Corrections

As the table, it can be seen that many prisons are over capacity by more than 400%, of course this has an impact on the rights of prisoners who neglected by the State, among others, the right to get comfort, health, safety and many more. The correctional system is regulated in Article 2 of Law Number 12 Year of 1995 concerning Corrections which reads as follows, "The penitentiary system is organized in order to form prisoners to become fully human, aware of mistakes, improve themselves, and not repeat criminal acts so they can be accepted back by community environment, can play an active role in development, and can live naturally as good and responsible citizens".

Other data shows the comparative condition of the occupancy rate of the number of Correctional Assistance Residents with the existing capacity, namely the Jakarta Narcotics Prison has a capacity of 1084 people compared to the occupancy rate of 2656 people, the Class IIA Tangerang Youth Prison has a capacity of approximately 1400 people with an occupancy rate of 2005 people, also Class I prisons. Tangerang has a capacity of 600 people with an occupancy rate of 1051 people. Class IIA Bogor Prison has a capacity of 634 people with an occupancy rate of 1039 people.

In Law Number 12 Year of 1995 concerning Corrections, prisoners have rights that must be granted during the process of training in a correctional institution. In Article 14 paragraph (1) and (2), it is stated that

prisoners have the right for, “a). perform worship according to their religion or belief; b). receive care, both spiritual and physical care; c). get education and teaching; d). get proper health services and food; e). submit a complaint; f). obtain reading material and follow other mass media broadcasts that are not prohibited; g). get wages or premiums for the work performed; h). receive visits from family, legal counsel, or certain other people; i). get a reduced sentence (remission); j). get the opportunity to assimilate including leave to visit family; k). get parole; l). get leave before being released; and m). obtain the other rights in accordance with the prevailing laws and regulations”. In order to carry out the granting of prisoners’ rights, then in carrying out guidance within the correctional institution must see :

1. Building pattern and layout.
2. Quality and quantity of Officers.
3. Prison Management.
4. Officer Welfare.
5. Development Facilities.
6. Budget.
7. Natural resources.
8. Quality and Development Programs

Based on the above review, the rights of prisoners must be given proportionately, however, the lack of supporting facilities and infrastructure for guidance can lead to less effective coaching, such as skills development requiring adequate equipment to directly practice theory in a coaching so that the success of the training can be assessed for its success. Law enforcement factors greatly affect the effectiveness of guiding prisoners in prisons. Based on the cases that occurred above, it shows that the problem that often occurs in prisons is over capacity. The excess capacity of the Correctional Assistance Citizens in prisons is one of the obstacles in the implementation of the ideal Correctional system. In Law Number 12 Year of 1995 concerning Corrections, article 45 point 4, it is written that the Correctional Observer Team consisting of prison officials or other relevant officials is tasked with: (a) providing advice on forms and programs of guidance and guidance in implementing the correctional system; (b) make an assessment of the implementation of the guidance and guidance program.

Ironically or contrary to the reality on the ground where one recent condition occurred, such as the riot in the Class IIA Banda Aceh Prison in January 2018, then other events that occurred such as the escape of 113 prisoners from the Class IIA Banda Aceh Prison in November 2018, in which the incident occurred. the prisoner escaped after breaking through the fence and window. There should be an improvement in conditions in the field because the legal rules already exist as written in the article 45. It should be the case that the above events, such as riots in prisons, or the fleeing of prisoners in prison, should not happen again. The five most densely populated prisons in Indonesia are: (1) Bagan Siapi-api Prison with a capacity of 98 people but has 810 people or over capacity of up to 836 percent, (2) Takengon detention center has a capacity of 65 people but has 495 people or 685 percent over capacity, (3) Banjarmasin prison has a capacity of 366 people but has 2,688 people or 664 percent over capacity, (4) Tarakan prison has a capacity of 155 people but has 996 people or over 650 percent capacity, (5) Labuhan Ruku prison has a capacity of 300 people but 1,770 people or over capacity of 640 percent. Prison occupants who are very large and exceed capacity, resulting in unbalanced security. On average, one prison guard supervises 34 prisoners.

Based on the above provisions, this indicates that the standards for detention rooms and guidance for inmates in prisons have been strictly regulated. However, the correctional facility has come under criticism for the treatment of prisoners. Among them are about inmates who died in prison. Most of the prisoners who died because they had suffered from illness before going to prison, and while in prison their health conditions were getting worse due to lack of care, low nutrition of food, and poor sanitation in the prison environment. This is due to the low number of facilities in the prison. Especially regarding the number of detainees living in the detention room which is not balanced (overcapacity).

As the case that occurred on Wednesday, June 13th, 2012 in the Garut Penitentiary, West Java, who died in prison. A prisoner in the motorcycle snatching case who was sentenced to 4 years in prison died of

respiratory illness he suffered. Based on this case, it shows that the correctional facilities built are not representative, causing many prisoners to get sick. This happens because the government is not capable of realizing the idea of a correctional facility because of the limited facilities / infrastructure resulting in less optimal development of prisoners in prisons. As stated by the Acting Head of the Class II B Correctional Institution in Sorong, the Class II B Penitentiary in Sorong City, West Papua has very few facilities, lack of facilities, especially regarding work facilities, namely in workshops and training. In addition, a similar thing also happened in the Tanjung Gusta Women's Class II A Penitentiary, Medan, inadequate facilities or facilities have become an obstacle to development and even become one of the causes of vulnerability to security / order and become one of the factors inhibiting the smooth process of implementing coaching for inmates because of all of these things are the cause of unsafe and disorderly conditions in prisons. Lack of supporting facilities for coaching can lead to ineffective coaching, because coaching such as skills coaching requires adequate equipment to directly practice theory in coaching so that it can be judged that the guidance carried out is successful or not.

The lack of human resources (HR) of correctional officers, both in number and in quality of integrity, is another problem in the correctional environment. If in the question is about the number of human resources, then the Ministry of Law and Human Rights has opened candidates for civil servants procurement vacancies throughout 2018. Of course, this can be categorized as the right solution in overcoming the problem of human resource shortages in prisons. However, another problem could be the quality of HR integrity. This needs special attention from the government, especially the ranks of the Ministry of Law and Human Rights. Examples of cases of the quality of the integrity of correctional human resources is, the Head of Purworejo Prison Cahyono Adhi Satriyanto was arrested by the joint team of the National Narcotics Agency (BNN) and the Central Java Provincial National Narcotics Agency (BNNP) in Purworejo on Monday, January 15th, 2018. He was arrested for providing easy access to control drugs in prisons by Christian Jaya Kusuma as Sancai. How can it be said that the correctional system works well if an event like him happens.

CONCLUSION

Facility factor, namely the lack of proper facilities in the correctional facility. This is due to the fact that the correctional facilities built are not representative and the limited facilities / infrastructure, resulting in less optimal development of prisoners in the correctional institutions. Over capacity is a problem that has never been resolved. This causes many problems in prisons. There have been many riots in several prisons because of this over capacity, however until now there has been no solution. Lack of human resources (HR) of correctional officers, both in number and in quality of integrity, is another problem in the correctional environment, which until now has not been resolved. From the two problems above, it can be concluded that prison governance in Indonesia is still lacking and far from expectations, there needs to be a commitment from the government in terms of law enforcement, provision of facilities and infrastructure and improvement of Human Resources.

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